

INCIDENCE AND SEVERITY OF BACTERIAL GRAIN ROT DISEASE IN RICE PLANTS WITH DIFFERENT CROPPING SYSTEMS

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Abstract

This study aims to compare the incidence and severity of bacterial grain rot disease in rice plants using anorganic, organic and natural farming systems. This research consist of several stages: 1) Preparation of farmers' rice fields using anorganic, organic and natural farming systems. 2) Observation of disease symptoms. 3) Measurement of disease incidence. 4) Severity measurement. Data were analyzed using variance analysis followed by post hoc tests and Duncan tests. Research data shows that the highest average of disease incidence is in anorganic farming systems (95.8%). The highest average of disease severity was in the organic farming system (57.6%). Based on the variance test, the incidence and severity of disease in natural and organic farming systems are not significantly different, while the incidence and severity of disease in natural and anorganic farming systems and organic and anorganic farming systems are significantly different.

Keywords: Incidence, Severity, Burkholderia, Organic, Natural.

INTRODUCTION

Rice is still the main commodity producing staple food in Indonesia. Various efforts are optimised to increase rice production to meet consumption needs and hopefully become self-sufficient in food and even surplus. On the one hand, rice production has decreased by 2.05% (BPS, 2023). Disease is a factor that plays a major role in causing the decline in production, one of which is grain rot and panicle rot caused by the bacterium *Burkholderia glumae* (Kurita and Tabei 1967; Urakami et al., 1994).

This disease can cause yield losses of 20% to 75%, and can even cause crop loss (Baharuddin et al., 2017; Trung et al., 1993). The presence of this disease has been reported in various articles in different parts of the world for more than several decades (Andrea and Fernando, 2014; Jeong et al., 2003; Kim et al., 2010; Luo et al., 2007; Nandakumar et al., 2009; Riera-Ruiz et al., 2014; Shahjahan et al., 2000; Trung et al., 1993) since it was first reported in Japan (Goto and Ohata, 1956). Early symptoms were described by Fory et al. (2014) in the form of brown dots or lines on the grain. Further symptoms include upright panicles because the seeds are not fully filled, green upright panicle twigs with green branch bones. Typical symptoms on the spikelets are marked by the formation of lines so that there appears to be a gradation of colour in the lemma and palea (discoloration) (Jeong et al. 2003).

Many studies have been conducted regarding the development of symptoms and incidence of BGR disease to determine how this disease affects rice growth and production. Widarti et al. (2020) observed and studied the symptoms and incidence of BGR disease in several rice varieties based on altitude. Another study was conducted by observing disease incidence in

several varieties to determine their resistance to BGR disease (Jazman et al., 2020) Several treatments carried out in the form of the use of chemicals and seed treatments were also unable to suppress the appearance of symptoms of the disease.

On the other hand, the farming system applied by farmers can affect disease incidence and severity. Common farming systems applied by farmers are anorganic farming systems that rely on synthetic fertilisers and pesticides, organic farming systems which are the opposite of anorganic farming systems, and natural farming systems that rely on ecological processes without synthetic inputs. Research of Nuryanto (2017) shows that different farming systems can affect the presence and severity of diseases in rice plants, for example, the use of mature compost enriched with antagonistic bacteria in organic farming systems can suppress the germination of sclerosia of *Rhizoctonia solani*, the pathogen that causes sheath blight in rice. In addition, the diversity of natural enemies in organic paddy rice ecosystems is higher compared to non-organic rice, which can help in the biological control of various pathogens (Hadi, 2018).

However, specifically for bacterial grain rot, information on the relationship between farming systems and the incidence and severity of this disease is limited. The study by Widarti et al. (2020) identified the presence of *Burkholderia glumae* in several rice varieties in West Java, but did not specifically address the influence of farming systems on this disease. Therefore, further research is needed to understand how natural, organic and anorganic farming systems affect the incidence and severity of bacterial grain rot disease in rice. This understanding is important for the development of effective and sustainable disease control strategies to improve rice productivity and resilience.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Area: The research was conducted in Salassae Village, Bulukumpa Sub-district, Bulukumba District, South Sulawesi Province, which is geographically located at the position of 120011'39.252"E-5022'24,108" S. The land used was farmer's land that applies natural, organic and anorganic farming systems.

Research Design: The research was conducted using a group randomised design (RAK) with three treatments including natural cultivation system, organic cultivation system and anorganic cultivation system. Each treatment consisted of three replicates. Each treatment consisted of three replicates, resulting in nine observation points. Each paddy field plot was set three observation units diagonally with an area of 1 m² so that if the spacing is 25 cm x 25 cm, there will be 16 clumps per unit.

Disease Symptom Observation: Observations made are direct measurements using an individual approach to disease objects in the form of disease symptoms. . Observations were made on plant parts including flag leaves, panicles, grains, and clumps as a whole. The observation time was carried out in the primordia phase at the age of 71-80 days after planting (hst). Observations were made for five weeks with a span of 7 days. Data obtained from these observations were then correlated with the presence (incidence) and severity (severity) of bacterial grain rot disease in the observation area.

Disease Incidence: Disease incidence (%) was measured by comparing diseased plants (diseased plant parts) with all observed plants (all plant parts).

Calculate the disease incidence using the formula:

$$\text{Incidence of the disease (\%)} = \frac{n}{N} \times 100\%$$

N : number of diseased clumps

N : number of clumps observed (16 clumps)

Disease severity: Bacterial grain rot disease severity was observed using disease severity scoring following the method of Karki et al. (2012) using a scale of 0-9 (Table 1).

Table 1: Severity Scoring of Bacterial Grain Rot Disease in Rice Plants.

Scale	Disease Symptoms
0	No symptomatic tillers
1	10% symptomatic tillers
2	11 – 20% symptomatic tillers
3	21 – 30% symptomatic tillers
4	31 – 40% symptomatic tillers
5	41 – 50% symptomatic tillers
6	51 – 60% symptomatic tillers
7	61 – 70% symptomatic tillers
8	71 – 80% symptomatic tillers
9	>80% symptomatic tillers

From the scoring observations, then calculate the severity of bacterial grain rot disease using the formula used by Masnilah et al. (2020):

KpP : Disease severity

N : number of tillers with a certain score

V : score value of each infection category

N : number of plants observed

Z : highest scale score

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA), if significantly different followed by Post-hoc test using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

RESULT

Disease Symptom: Early symptoms appear in the panicle and flower development phase at 71 - 80 Days after planting (HST) where there are lesions on the flag leaf. The next symptom that appears is on the spikelets starting to turn grey to dark brown (Fig. 1).

Symptoms on the spikelets vary, where there are spikelets that only have small blackish-brown spots such as symptoms on spikelets attacked by walang sangit pests, there are also spikelets that are half dark brown, to blackish-brown as a whole. The panicles stood upright because the spikelets were not fully filled but the panicle stalks remained green. At the milk ripening phase, almost all the tillers begin to show symptoms. In detail, the symptoms of bacterial grain rot disease caused by *B. Glumae* on parts of the rice plant can be seen in Figure 2.

Disease Incidence: Observations and measurements of disease incidence were observed since the first symptoms appeared, namely in the primordia phase at 71-80 hst. Observations were made for six weeks to determine the presence of Bacterial Grain Rot disease as well as to see the development of disease symptoms. The first symptoms appeared on rice plants with anorganic cultivation systems. In organic and natural cultivation systems, the symptoms of the disease only appeared in the second week of observation.

Based on the data in Figure 1, the highest disease incidence every week was found in the anorganic cultivation system, where the disease incidence reached 81.3% at the end of the observation. Early symptoms also appeared in the first week of observation only in the anorganic cultivation system, while in the organic and natural cultivation systems it only appeared in the second week of observation.

Based on the analysis of variance data, disease incidence based on observation time was not significantly different in each treatment in the first and second week of observation. While the third week to the fifth week was significantly different in each treatment. Based on the treatment, namely the application of cultivation systems, disease incidence in natural and organic cultivation systems was not significantly different, while anorganic and organic cultivation systems or anorganic and natural cultivation systems were significantly different.

Disease Severity: Observations and measurements of disease severity were also observed since the first symptoms appeared, namely in the panicle and flower development phase. The measurement of disease severity was done by observing the scoring of disease symptoms associated with the number of symptomatic plants. Observations were conducted for six weeks to determine the severity of Bacterial Grain Rot disease as well as to see the development of disease symptoms. Symptoms first appeared on rice plants under anorganic cultivation systems. In the organic and natural cultivation systems, symptoms only appeared in the second week of observation.

Based on the data in Figure 2, the highest disease severity was found in the anorganic cultivation system, reaching 51.4% at the end of the observation. Because the initial symptoms in the first week of observation were only found in the anorganic cultivation system, the disease severity was measured only in this cultivation system, while the organic and natural cultivation systems only appeared in the second week of observation.

Based on the analysis of variance data, disease severity based on observation time was not significantly different in each treatment in the first and second weeks of observation. While the third week to the fifth week was significantly different in each treatment. Based on the treatment, namely the application of the cultivation system, disease severity in natural and organic cultivation systems was not significantly different, while anorganic and organic cultivation systems or anorganic and natural cultivation systems were significantly different.

DISCUSSION

Disease Symptom: The symptoms found in the field are in accordance with several previous studies. Widarti, et al. (2020) and Kurniasih, et al. (2020) suggested that disease symptoms are marked by panicles stretching upwards because the seeds are not fully filled, green upright panicle twigs with green branch bones and colour gradations on the grains. Symptoms of this disease generally appear in the generative phase and infect rice grains so that it will have a direct impact on reducing rice production. Jeong et al. (2003) reported that *B. glumae* attack in Korea can cause yield losses of up to 34%. Yield reduction due to bacterial grain rot disease in Vietnam reached 75% in the form of decreased grain weight, sterile flowers, inhibition of germination and decreased production (Trung et al. 1993). The losses caused by this bacterium reached 40% in 1995-1999 in some rice production areas in Arkansas (Shahjahan et al. 2000).

Disease Incidence: Disease symptoms, incidence and severity are found in all cropping systems as they relate to several factors necessary for infection to occur. Lee et al. (2004) stated that there are 3 factors that affect the ability and success of bacterial infection, namely temperature, humidity and plant growth phase. The plant growth phase that most determines the success of infection is heading time (40% panicle emergence). Disease incidence was highly correlated with daily temperature for 7 and 10 days with minimum relative humidity for 15 days from 3 days before and 3 days after heading time. High temperature and humidity in the flowering phase are conducive conditions for bacterial infection (Tsushima 1996). *B. Glumae* can live at 20-41 °C, with optimum conditions at 30-31 °C, and is suitable for warm night conditions with a high frequency of rain (Nandakumar 2009; Cui et al. 2016). Toxoflavin as one of the virulence factors is only produced at 25-37 °C.

CONCLUSION

Disease symptoms begin to appear in the panicle and flower development phase at 71 - 80 Days after planting (HST) where there are lesions on the flag leaf. The next symptom that appears is on the grain starting to be grey to dark brown. Symptoms on the spikelets vary, where there are spikelets that only have small blackish-brown spots. The panicles stand upright because the spikelets are not fully filled but the panicle stalk remains green. The highest disease incidence every week was found in the anorganic cultivation system, where the disease incidence reached 81.3% at the end of the observation before harvest. The highest disease severity in the first week to the fifth week was found in the anorganic cultivation system, but in the sixth week was found in the organic cultivation system with disease severity reaching 51.4% at the end of the observation before harvest.

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